

An Overview of the Strategic Management Practices in Non-Profit Organizations - Case Study UK

Robin Okuthe*

^a *robin.okuthe@muk.ac.ug*
Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, 2018

Abstract

Research aims and objectives: The research aimed to explore the strategic management practices in NPOs operating in the UK. The study drew on a resource dependence conceptual framework to explore the strategic management practices in NPOs in the UK.

Research methods: The study used interpretivist philosophy as a research approach. Consistent with the inductive approach, a qualitative case study research method was used in the study. Primary data was collected using semi-structured interviews while secondary data was collected using document analysis. Seven semi-structured interviews were carried out. Semi-structured interviews were employed to collect participant's perspectives, which in turn complimented the information generated from a critical review of the literature on account of document analysis.

Research findings: The study established that external environmental factors have greater influence over strategic management practices NPOs in the UK than internal environmental factors. The practices are mainly designed to solve problems expected in the external environment. This illustrates that NPOs in the UK have defective strategic management practices targeted at external environment, other than both the internal and external environment.

Recommendations: NPOs in the UK should also aim to address their external and internal environmental problems, as part of their long-term strategy. NPOs in the UK should also pursue a more balanced model that emphasizes both donors and clients, or a hybrid between a market-oriented and donor-oriented model that would potentially enable them to 'balance money and mission.'

Keywords: NPOs in the UK, strategic management practices, defective strategic management practices, Strategic management of non-profit organizations, stakeholder management

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Strategic management of non-profit organizations in the United Kingdom is increasingly becoming complex owing to unprecedented levels of technological advancements, greater pressures for accountability by funders and the general public, as well as the greater diversity of stakeholders in an increasingly globalized world (Hecht & Ramsey 2002). Since the 2000s, the UK non-profit and charity sector has undergone rapid expansion in scale and scope. Such developments have, in turn, considerably affected how the non-profit organizations (NPOs) should be managed. For instance, it has prompted non-profit managers to consider developing a market mindset, whereby they emphasize ensuring competitive advantages and financial sustainability of their firms (Macedo & Pinho 2004; Othman et al. 2014). Indeed, as Macedo and Pinho (2004) explained, non-profit managers have realized that their new missions entail attempting to influence donors to donate, volunteers to engage in voluntary works, clients to be more responsive, and employees to be client-friendly, accountable and transparent.

Research has shown that non-profit managers find it difficult in gaining absolute control over the affairs and the environment in which their organizations operate in the twenty-first century (Hecht & Ramsey 2002; Holatova & Dolezalova, 2014). However, there appears to be a consensus among management and social researchers that adopting strategic management in these organizations can enable non-profit managers to adequately, address, influence, and get ready for the complexity of demands of their operating and external environment (Holatova & Dolezalova, 2014). Indeed, some scholars have recommended a need to use formal-strategy formation processes - such as structured strategic planning model - owing to their potential to encourage transparent decision-making, and greater levels of accountability (Anheier 2009; 2003; Bryson 2004).

Compared to the management teams of organizations designed for a commercial purpose that have significant pressures to achieve operational efficiency and financial prosperity, the management teams of NPOs are usually not experienced or skilled in strategic management practices (Othman et al. 2014). An underlying reason for this is that NPOs emphasize voluntary participation and amiability and establishing informal relationships, which in turn alienates the notion of overt accountability. Such intrinsic attributes of NPOs have made them stress less on management accounting and control practices provided that they achieve their social missions and values. However, such attributes are problematic for NPOs because of the changing operational environment (Hecht & Ramsey 2002). In the case of the United Kingdom, insufficiency and a dearth of accounting information are causing NPOs to fail to benefit from financial sustainability improvement and expansion and to leverage the strategic skills for predicting failures and implementing advanced financial planning and control mechanism (Acevo 2017). While some commentators have reasoned that this is because of lack of availability of resources and funding, some NPOs have underscored the need to implant the principle of accountability in all faced of their operations, as all organizations, in spite of their nature, have to be answerable to their stakeholders.

It appears that non-profit organizations in the UK have either failed or have been slow to adopt strategic management “best practices” (Acevo 2017). In turn, the management of these organizations has been exposed to uncertainty regarding how they can restructure strategic management practices of their organizations. These form the basis of this research.

1.2 Research Problem

NPOs in the UK are evolving and adjusting to address complex demands, including conforming to government pressures to be accountable and transparent in their financial management, responding to the changing external environment and the demands of beneficiaries. Similarly, they are confronted by greater levels of scrutiny from the public through social media platforms, the mainstream media, and funders particularly after the fall of Kids Company -- which revealed how some NPOs engage in inappropriate fundraising and mismanage funds (Acevo 2017).

The UK charity and social sector is a fundamental part component of the UK social fabric, with an estimated 160,000 registered NPOs in England and Wales, and some other community social groups and social enterprises. However, these organizations are encumbered by poor strategic management practices, leading to lack of stability of their incomes. For instance, NPOs with incomes ranging from £25,000 and £1 million tend to experience financial volatility, with nearly one-third of these NPOs being highly susceptible to external shocks due to bad management (Acevo 2017).

Some cases of NPO employee fraud, organizational mismanagement, and collapse have been noted in the UK. An example includes the collapse of a London youth work non-profit organization called Kids Company in 2015. The organization was found to have collapsed as a result of financial management problems (Elgot, 2015). The organization was overwhelmed by financial turmoil after the UK government canceled its annual £5 million grant. It was later accused of lacking an efficient governance structure, inability to incorporate “best practices” in governance, employee fraud, and financial mismanagement (The Guardian, 2015).

Despite the fact that internal functioning problems, as opposed to financial problems, are beginning to be appreciated by NPOs as drivers to internal control problem and management failures, they have received nominal attention, particularly in the UK. Additionally, NPOs with weak financial control mechanisms are likely to report an internal control problem and management failures. However, there appears to be a dearth of research as regards the extent to which strategic management practices of NPOs in the UK vary from the management of conventional profit-making businesses, and how NPOs are adopting effective strategies to ensure their long-term financial and competitive sustainability (Holatova & Dolezalova, 2014; Macedo and Pinho, 2004; Othman et al., 2014).

Against this background, it becomes clear that NPOs with weak financial control mechanisms are likely to report an internal control problem and management failures. In spite of the idea that internal functioning problems, as opposed to financial problems, are beginning to be appreciated by NPOs as drivers to internal control problem and management failures, they have received nominal attention, particularly in the UK.

1.3 Research Purpose

This research proceeds from the supposition that current management and organizational research have not adequately addressed the question of strategic management of NPOs in the UK, and whether they should be managed distinctly from the profit-driven business firm and whether they should be managed using different management practices and models. The study explored the strategic management practices of NPOs in the UK to determine their variation from the management of conventional profit-making businesses, and to determine how they can form effective strategies to ensure their long-term sustainability.

1.4 Research aims and objectives

The aim of the research is to explore the strategic management practices in NPOs operating in the UK.

The main study objectives include:

- Explore the strategic management practices used by NPOs in the UK;
- Investigate the strategic management models used by NPOs;
- Determine how strategic practices of NPOs differ from those of for-profit organizations;
- Examine the effects of NPO's external environmental and internal context on strategy formation processes;

- Investigate how Organizations in the UK respond to changes in the internal and external environment;
- Determine the reasons for strategic management by NPOs in the UK.

1.5 Research Questions

Building on research aims and objectives, the proposed research questions include:

- What strategic management practices do NPOs in the UK use?
- What strategic models do NPOs in the UK use?
- In what ways do your strategic management practices of NPOs differ from those of for-profit organizations?
- How does UK NPO's external environmental and internal context and strategy formation processes influence the strategies they use?
- How do NPOs in the UK set up strategic management strategies to respond to changes in the internal and external environment?
- What reasons underlie the use of strategic management in NPOs in the UK?

1.6 Significance

Strategic management of NPOs is a complex and uncertain endeavor for NPO executives and boards of management. This study will contribute to knowledge on how poor strategic management can contribute to poor service delivery and collapse of NPOs and how these can be avoided through appropriate strategic management practices. By proving an improved understanding of strategic management practices and their implications, the proposed study hopes that NPOs will be able to attain greater financial sustainability. This will also have a theoretical significance as it will generate greater insights into the variation between management practices of NPOs and profit-making businesses to inform empirical research and organizational practices.

1.7 Theoretical Framework

The study drew on a resource dependence conceptual framework to explore the strategic management practices in non-profit organizations. The resource-dependence theory hypothesizes that an organization's behavior is influenced by the extent of its resource dependencies (Hillman et al., 2009). It attempts to demonstrate that external factors will almost automatically influence organizational behavior and, while organizations will be restricted by their contexts, their management teams can develop strategies to limit their vulnerability to environmental uncertainty and dependencies. Salancik and Pfeffer (1978) proposed the theory in their works "The External Control of Organizations: A Resource Dependence Perspective." To date, the theory has been applied as a framework for organizational theory and strategic management research. Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) argued that for organizations to survive, they require resources (such as capital, labor, legitimacy, and clientele) that external factors control, which causes interdependencies that may contribute to an imbalance of power over who should control them. When these resources are scarce, the funders or suppliers of these resources have greater power, which may lead the organization to lose autonomy and an ability to freely undertake managerial and strategic discretion as required (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978).

NPO's revenue structure and management practices present an opportunity to understand the manner in which they behave and the management practices they adopt. Their fate also depends on the extent to which they can access resources (Verbruggen et al., 2009). By basing on this assumption, it is reasoned that the specific type of resource dependence by NPOs in the UK may also explain the manner in which they behave and the management practices they adopt. Previous studies have successfully applied the resource dependence framework to NPOs and have demonstrated that the theory

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provides an essential theoretical model for exploring problem assessments, perspectives, and strategies used by non-profit-making organizations (Macedo & Pinho, 2004).

1.8 Dissertation structure

Part 1 of this dissertation consists of the Introduction chapter. It discusses research background on how NPOs in the UK have either failed or have been slow to adopt strategic management “best practices. It also consists of the research problem regarding how such NPOs are likely to report an internal control problem and management failures. It also outlines the research purpose, research aims and objectives, research questions and significance, and a discussion of the theoretical framework.

Part 2 of the dissertation consists of the literature review section. It consists of a review of previous research on strategic management practices in NPOs, strategic management models used by NPOs’ strategic management practices and their variation from management of for-profit organizations, influence of NPOs’ external and internal environmental context on strategy formation and use, developing a strategic plan in response to changes internal and external environment, and reasons for strategic management by NPOs.

Part 3 of the dissertation consists of the research methodology section. It discusses the research philosophy used along with the research paradigm, the qualitative research methods and approach used data collection method and sampling procedures, and a discussion on ethical considerations.

Part 4 consists of the data analysis section and discusses the research findings. Part 5 consists of the discussion section and attempts to interpret and explain the implication of research findings in the reflection of what is already known regarding the research problems examined. It also describes new insights regarding the research problems.

Part 6 consists of the Conclusion and recommendation section. Here, findings of the research are summarized to how they have contributed to research knowledge on strategic management practices of NPOs in the UK, their failures and recommendations.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Strategic management practices in NPOs

A non-profit organization (NPO) has largely been described as an organization whose “predominantly non-business characteristics” significantly influence its operations that are designed to carry out a social mission, create social value, or deliver public benefits as opposed to generating profit (Othman et al., 2014). In the last decade, the non-profit and charity sector has experienced rapid expansion in scope, which demonstrates their increased significance in the society. Such developments have significantly affected how the NPOs are managed by prompting non-profit managers to develop a market mindset (Macedo & Pinho 2004; Othman et al. 2014). Indeed, as Macedo and Pinho (2004) explained non-profit managers have realized that their new missions entail influencing donors to donate.

Related literature has demonstrated that a market-oriented mindset has significant advantages in terms of encouraging efficiency in profit-driven business firms. It encourages organizations to design the most suitable services to the target clients and can enable sustainable competitive advantage by encouraging organizations to create superior customer value and better organizational performance (Macedo & Pinho 2004; Othman et al. 2014). Macedo and Pinho (2004) argue that adopting resource-based strategies can enable NPOs to adopt a change of attitude with respect to obtaining and managing their funding sources and their management strategies. Put differently, NPOs must seek ways to efficiently manage their resources more efficiently to improve their performance in an increasingly complex internal and external environment.

A relevant body of research exists that accounts for the basic dynamics linked to the environmental effect on organizations and how they can react to environmental limitations to their management capacity. The assumption is built

on the resource dependence theory, which contends that organizations can attain ultimate survival depending on their capacity to obtain and maintain resources (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978, p. 2).

The origin of strategic management can be traced to the mid-1980s, which was marked by a growth rate of competition, increased pressures for innovation, and a rise in a tendency to be more customer-oriented. The objective of management practices was to establish and understand strategies that would embody a competitive advantage (Holatova & Dolezalova, 2014). Similarly, organizations of non-profit sector started using principles of strategic management to a great extent. Strategic management refers to a combination of managerial decisions and activities that can be applied in the facilitation of competitive advantage and long-term superior organizational performance. They focus on limiting organizational weaknesses and leveraging their strengths and anticipating future problems and likely opportunities. Within the context of NPOs, Holatova and Dolezalova (2014) observed that strategic management is usually typified by diverse expectations and purposes of varied stakeholders, influencing donors, multi-source financing, attracting grants from governments and sponsors. Previous studies that examined strategic management and organizational effectiveness mostly used mixed research and qualitative research methods.

A study by Herman and Renz (2004) used a qualitative research approach to investigate local nonprofit organizations' effectiveness. They concentrated on two nonprofit organizations. The first was a health and welfare service provider that was funded by the local United Way. The second attended to developmentally disabled children. They surveyed 30 respondents. Their study established a relationship between the effectiveness of the board and the effectiveness of the organization. There also appeared to be a consensus among respondents that an adjustment in the use of management practices was not linked to a shift in opinion regarding the overall effectiveness of the organizations.

In a related qualitative research study, Courtney et al. (2009) interviewed CEOs of nonprofit organizations to determine the strategic management approaches they used. The researchers collected data using in-depth interviews with housing nonprofit organizations. They categorized the organizations under "sophistication" and "approach." In the "approach" category, they developed a four-category typology building on the alternatives that the organization can pursue growth. Under the sophistication category, they developed a three-category building on the tools and techniques the organization applied in strategic planning. Their findings indicated a strong relationship between the size of the organization and sophistication in strategic planning. While the larger sized firms indicated high-performance ratings, the smaller ones indicated lower performance.

Rehor et al. (2014) examined strategic management methods in NPOs. Based on systematic review of the literature, they revealed that NPOs tend to focus their strategic management practices towards solving problems identified in the external environment. Current literature has shown that the failure or success of NPOs is essentially contingent on strategic decision-making. Related literature has indicated that strategic management should make sure that organizational management did not occur randomly but based on clarified long-term objectives (Weerawardena & Mort, 2012). According to Weerawardena and Mort (2012), NPO leaders should be open to shifting goals and activities with regards to changing situations in the external or internal environments. As a result, organizational leaders need to consistently, monitor, evaluate, and benefit from constant feedback. It is on this basis that strategic management could be reasoned as a fluid, and ongoing approach, as opposed to a one-shot approach.

Rehor et al. (2014) contend that strategic management should also be considered as a process and a means of contemplating about particular aspects of an organization like long- and short-term goals, stakeholders, and achieving efficiency. It is a continuous intricate process of management that agrees on the organizational targets and a strategic course for reaching specific targets. To this end, strategic management can be interpreted as a combination of management decisions and action plans that the management can employ to enable competitive advantage and long-term better

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performance of an organization. As a consequence, it potentially reduces organizational weaknesses and leverages their strengths by anticipating prospects and problems.

Within the context of NPOs, strategic management is distinguished by diverse functions and expectations of different groups, impacts of donors, funding from multiple sources, and a high fraction of resources from sponsors. As a consequence, for successful strategic management of an organization, it has to be aware of issues regarding its reasons for its existence, changes in the needs and structures of the organization over time, and whether it has adequate human and financial resources (Weerawardena et al., 2010).

Seemingly, the nonprofit sector is attracting an increased volume of research to explore the basis of successful value creation through strategic management. In an attempt to advance nonprofit sector research beyond its present emphasis on conceptualizing the concept of strategic management, Weerawardena and Mort (2012) used multiple theoretical case studies to examine the competitive strategy in socially entrepreneurial nonprofit organizations. They established that focus on ensuring the sustainability of for-profit businesses has prevailed in the strategic management literature for many decades. This discovered that the market orientation discourse, the resource advantage theory, and the resource-based view fundamentally reveal the necessity for-profit organizations to achieve competitive advantages that enabled them to grow and survive over the long-term.

In spite of this, the nonprofit literature seems not to reveal that NPOs have emphasized attaining competitive advantages to enable them to grow and survive over the long-term, in spite of an increasing rate of threats to their sustainability (Mort & Weerawardena, 2008).

Innate dissimilarities between for-profit and nonprofit organizations may prevent the direct use of theories derived from the business sector. Fundamentally, NPOs diverge considerably from the for-profit organizations in numerous considerable ways. For-profit organizations seek to persistently create greater shareholder wealth by delivering superior value to its customers. On the other hand, NPOs make significant efforts for financial resources to bring in social value to its stakeholders. Indeed, related literature on the NPOs operating environment indicate that these types of organizations operate in a highly complex and demanding multi-stakeholder environment and therefore require advanced strategic management processes (Kohli & Jaworski 1990).

2.2 Strategic Management Models used by NPOs

In an attempt to determine the approaches that nonprofits can use to develop their strategy, Courtney et al. (2009) used the term “sophistication” to define the strategic analysis, development, and implementation of strategic planning in organizations. The research interviewed chief executives and reviewed organization to develop a three-level sophistication scale consisting of an informal planner, partial planners, and full planners. In a later study, Courtney et al. (2009) also employed the term strategic approach to refer to the rules that organizations use to determine their operation scope. The process inspired the creation of four strategic approach categories: all opportunistic expansionists, opportunists, incrementalists, and niche strategists.

All opportunistic expansionists are a group of organizations that expand their scope of operations with time outside their original mission to cover new geographical areas. Opportunists consist of organizations that pursue innovation outside of their written plans and objectives. Incrementalists are organizations that have previously demonstrated an interest in extending beyond their mission yet have failed to capitalize on the existing opportunities to do so. Niche strategists are organizations that stick to their particular missions and objectives and have not considered expanding beyond their niche.

The “market orientation” model and the “market-driven firm paradigm” are significantly emphasized in for-profit literature and reveal the importance placed on satisfying and retaining customers. Weerawardena et al. (2010) observed that NPOs must lay a comparatively lower emphasis on clients than on donors. Although focusing on clients has a potential to ensure better service delivery in NPOs, the link between the clients and generation of revenue is fundamentally

detached in NPOs. According to Weerawardena et al. (2010), donors are placed at the center owing to the decisive role they play in the provision of revenue stream that is significant for the operation of an NPO. Also, governments and entrepreneurial business initiatives nested within the NPO have provided other important sources of finance for NPOs. Substantial volatility across all these diverse revenue streams forces NPOs to become adept at multiple stakeholder management.

Weerawardena et al. (2010) also attempted to focus on 'balancing money and mission' as the principal concern in the management of NPOs. Some theoretical models and experiential comparisons have considered such constructs as production quality, pricing, production quantity, improvement of service quality, and budgeting practice. An NPO needs to make sure there is a flow of resources to ensure long-term sustainability (Valentinov, 2008). NPOs obtain funding through, governmental support, earned income and donation from private entities.

Scholars who have contributed to this body of literature tend to suggest numerous strategies that NPOs can espouse to boost their financial substantiality. These include revenues generated commercially, using business principles to, strategic alliances and application of relationship marketing (Valentinov 2008; Weerawardena et al. 2010). Besides the strategies for generating revenues, scholars have proposed some strategies that can be employed to cut costs. These include greater productivity, greater soliciting of volunteerism and requesting for in-kind donations. There is also a concern that social entrepreneurs should be provided with economic autonomy to carry on with their operations. This assumption has its basis in the Schumpeterian view, which considers entrepreneurs as fundamental economic actors.

In the last decade, some scholars have arrived at a consensus that 'earned income strategies' can be used to attain organizational sustainability, which integrates the attributes of nonprofit with for-profit organizations (Peredo & McLean, 2006; Weerawardena et al. 2010). In a related study, Mair and Marti (2006) extended this perspective arguing that 'social entrepreneurship may also be effectively applied on a for-profit basis. Using case study qualitative research approach, Mair and Marti (2006) identified three 'social ventures' that have attempted this strategy. These include Grameen Bank in Bangladesh, Aravind Hospital in India, and Sekem Chemicals in Egypt.

As a consequence, the profits that these organizations generate from their principal activities are applied in engaging in numerous social ventures. For instance, Sekem in Egypt operates as a multi-business that has succeeded in reducing pesticides applied in cotton fields in Egypt by 90 percent. The organization has developed learning institutions and a health center (Seelos & Mair, 2005). Accordingly, Mair and Marti (2006) argued that 'the selection of the set-up is essentially directed by the types of the social needs tackled, the number of resources required, and the possibility of raising revenues.

2.3 Strategic Management Practices of NPOs and their Variation from Management of for-profit Organizations

The principal–agency theory hypothesizes that for-profit organizations are more efficient than nonprofit organizations as their managers aspire to increase shareholders' returns. On the other hand, nonprofits ought to provide an enhanced quality of services through service to the community, provision of charity, undertaking pieces of research, and invitation of philanthropic supporters. However, this difference is not evenly supported across the nonprofit literature. A blend of studies undertaken in the past two decades demonstrates disparities between for-profit and nonprofit organizations, yet the findings appear not to be conclusive and are somewhat conflicting in some cases (Reeves & Ford 2004).

Some studies have emphasized on differences in quality of care and profits. Costs and revenues affect the growth in equity and profits of organizations, in spite of how they are measured (Reeves & Ford 2004). Indeed, the costs and revenues are significant revenues that must constantly be taken into consideration in the assessment of measures that relate to them. According to Reeves and Ford (2004), nonprofit organizations tend to have lower levels of daily adjusted costs compared to for-profit organizations, such as those for Medicare psychiatric patients. The researcher showed that the rates

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for per capita Medicare spending and the rise in rates tended to be greater in areas dominated by for-profit organizations in comparison to those predominantly served by NPOs.

However, the entire cost categories tended to be high for for-profit organizations than for NPOs that operated as hospitals even after adjustments for taxes as the costs for administration costs were relatively high. According to Ettner and Hermann (2001), patients in NPO hospitals tended to have longer stays for each admission, which suggested that they were relatively less efficient in their operations. Shukla and Clement established conflicting results. They found that patients tended to stay longer in for-profit hospitals, which also had smaller staff-to-patient ratios. Consistent with this finding, King and Avery established that in the process of conversion to other forms, for-profit hospitals tended to reduce the nurse-to-patient ratio after they acquired a nonprofit hospital, cut redundant programs, did away with research and educational programs, and reduced community welfare and health initiatives. While Mark established very nominal dissimilarity, in spite of whether for-profit hospitals transformed to nonprofit hospitals or nonprofit hospitals transformed to for-profit ones, NPOs showed a remarkable tendency to boost staff-to-patient ratios once they acquired a for-profit hospital.

In a related study, Mobley and Magnussen assessed long-term and short-term efficiency, which they delineated as a rise in a single output that requires a reduction in a different output or arises in at least a single input — as was in the case of hospitals in California. In the long-term, the researchers established that the for-profit hospitals tended to have substantially lower levels of group-wise efficiency compared to non-profit hospitals in urban California.

2.4 Influence of NPO's External and Internal Environmental Context on Strategy Formation and Use

Researchers have attempted to explain how NPOs external environmental and internal context and strategy formation processes influence how strategic management practices are implemented (Giffords & Dina, 2004). It appears that there is no real consensus on how this should happen. However, some scholars like Giffords and Dina (2004) emphasized that NPOs rely on strategic planning to prioritize the strategies they use in their internal and external environments.

In their view, the main advantage of creating a strategic plan within the framework of continuous quality and performance improvement (CQPI) is to enable nonprofit's management and employees to acclimatize the organization to the existing internal and external environment, prioritize the organization's mission, and illuminate client's needs (Hoonakker et al. 2010). As Wilbur (2000) reveals, this ongoing process sustains the necessity for NPOs to continually improve quality services to their clients while revealing to their funders and other concerned stakeholders that the organization has a positive effect on them.

Giffords and Dina (2004) define strategic planning as a systematic process that assists in bringing a consensus as regards organizational priorities among the primary stakeholders to assist an organization to meet its mission (Wilbur, 2000). Within the context of NPOs, strategic planning is more complicated than planning in the for-profit organizations, whereby managers aim to increase shareholder's wealth. At any rate, it is concerned with the systematic management of external and internal conditions of an NPO's environment. The base on which plans are built is through assessments of these environments. However, the external and internal environmental context influence the strategies that NPOs use.

While evaluating an NPO's internal environment, the managers may discover conflicting perspectives of the organization's mission and vision, and degree of efficiency. Giffords & Dina (2004) expressed concern that individuals working in NPOs may find themselves becoming increasingly immersed in the everyday operation of the organizations, which may influence them to concentrate on "program ends rather than the purpose" they are intended to accomplish. Organizational cultures and values should as well be taken into consideration as they directly affect the organization's operation (Giffords & Dina, 2004). Accordingly, when the leadership of the organization seeks to create a strategic plan, they need first to undertake an internal analysis to discover issues that potentially affect the organization. Afterwards, they should endeavor to position those deemed vital within their organizations' context.

Steiner et al. (1994) identified internal indicators that enhance the urgency for planning, particularly in the increasingly aggressive nonprofit environment. These include periods of stagnant organizational growth and administrative operations, and high employee turnover or changes in leadership. The external environment is also essential to the functioning of nonprofit organizations, particularly in periods where there is a high competition for limited funds, changes in client priorities, shifts in accreditation requirements, and societal changes (Giffords & Dina, 2004).

2.5 Developing a Strategic Plan in Response to changes Internal and External Environment

According to Giffords and Dina (2004), CQPI is a valuable tool that NPOs can use to adapt to the changing external and internal environments. Nonprofit researchers like Pecora and Seelig (2001) support this assumption. Pecora and Seelig (2001) consider a CQPI plan as a systematic process for committing to the constituents of an organization, pledging to advance all areas of operation persistently. Giffords and Dina (2004) view it as an organization's pledge to its clients and the greater community to offer them efficient and effective services. This implies that the CQPI process is set up to build on evaluations of an organization's performance and to execute targeted improvements rapidly.

Mikulas and Cohan (2001) made a similar conclusion, stressing that setting up a CQPI implies that the planning, goal-setting and attainment activities of an organization are provided with information using a formal feedback process, including through external assessments, to bring about improved performance that is beneficial to both the organization and its constituents. However, the assessment should be accurate. As Giffords and Dina (2004) highlighted, having an accurate evaluation process is critical. This implies gathering accurate data regarding a problem and analyzing and interpreting it empirically. In the end, an accurate evaluation process has a potential to help an organization to obtain a comprehensible outlook of the future and to develop relevant goals. In the process of developing a strategic plan, organizations need to carefully decide whom to include in the planning process, including the board of directors, management staff, and some employees, as well as funders, some members of the community, clients, and volunteers. Steiner et al. (1994) advised that implementation of the strategic plan should then follow once it is developed. The organization's employees will need to take part in this process collectively.

2.6 Reasons for Strategic Management by NPOs

Many scholars agree that strategic planning helps NPOs to make informed decisions regarding their prospect (Ogonji 2014). In spite of the divergent opinion regarding the effectiveness of strategic planning, the models used should be able to generate reliable results to be acceptable (Mulhare, 1999). Although nonprofit organizations are supposed to be beneficial to the society at large, there are cases where the opposite happens. A study by Ogonji (2014) showed that a majority of volunteers tend to be uncertain of what the society looks forward to getting from them. The researcher mentioned incidences of embezzlement of public funds and cases where NPOs failed to live up to their stakeholders' expectations. According to Ogonji (2014), strategic planning enabled organizations to envisage the future and agree on what should be done to get there by adopting new approaches and developing a new shared vision. Similar results are reflected in Bryson's (2010) study. Bryson (2010) established that strategic management encourages strategic thinking and actions to respond to a situational issue in an organization. It leads to a clarification of vision, assists organizations to discover best strategies, promotes consensus- building among stakeholders and improves the capacity of organizations to make a quality decision that reflects back to organizational objectives and mission.

Strategic management also becomes useful when organizations change their scope of operation or mission. A study by Bryson & Alsto (2011) indicated the challenges constantly confronting nonprofits organizations that prompt them to set up strategic management. The researchers outlined that substantial rise in demand for services that NPOs offer, a greater level

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of competition, problems in the acquisition of funds, a desire to collaborate with other organizations, greater pressures for transparency and accountability and increased levels of doubt regarding economic, political and social changes of the future prompted NPOs to engage in strategic management. Ogonji (2014) validated these findings. He centered on the contemporary problems confronting nonprofits. They identified them as including income disparity between the poor and the rich, continually diminishing funding by the government, and increased pressures on NPOs to publish and explain results of their operation to donors owing to the general belief that they allocate a huge proportion of their budgets on overheads. Additional triggers identified in Ogonji's (2014) research include higher levels competition and innovativeness from social enterprises.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Philosophy

The study used interpretivist philosophy as a research approach (Saunders et al. 2003). The philosophy considers that it is strictly based on subjective interpretation of reality that makes sure that the reality can be wholly understood. The philosophy was considered to be appropriate for the study owing to its capacity to facilitate a survey of research participants in their natural setting and that it acknowledged that the researcher does not affect the phenomena under study (Creswell, 2002). Hence, it considers non-profit managers as having a capacity to construct meanings depending on how they interpret strategic management practices in NPOs. The interpretivist philosophy is selected for the study, as it depends on inductive reasoning.

An inductive approach was also used in the research to help examine the emergent generalizations from non-profit managers' perspectives strategic management practices of NPOs in the UK. The approach was used to facilitate the formation of emergent generalizations. It was considered to be appropriate for the study, as known premises would be used in the process of generating untested conclusions regarding strategic management practices of NPOs (Williams, 2007).

3.2 Research Paradigm

The study used interpretive paradigm, as it relates to how people attempt to make sense of their natural settings and construct meanings attached to their experiences in their natural setting. The objectives of the proposed research fall within an interpretive paradigm because they attempt to explore deep-seated meanings attached to strategic management practices.

3.3 Qualitative Research Method

Consistent with the inductive approach, a qualitative case study research method was used in the study. A qualitative research method presents a systematic approach for studying the phenomenon in participants' natural setting and to facilitate the development of research details from real experiences of the participants. The study used a case study research, as it is appropriate for explanatory and exploratory research. It is 'an empirical inquiry designed for investigating a contemporary phenomenon within their real-life contexts, in cases where the boundaries between research phenomenon and their context are particularly distinct, and where the research seeks for numerous sources of evidence (Yin 1984). Multiple case studies were used in this study as they are considered to be capable of providing more robust research results than single case studies.

The case study method was used in the research as it permits the grouping of different sources of evidence from semi-structured interviews and document analysis (Marrionto et al. 2012). To highlight the needs underscored in the review of the literature, the proposed study will utilize a mixed-method comparative multi-case study of a group of NPOs with similar operations in the areas of service offering, client needs, funding needs, technological complexity and changing competitive dynamics. The participants were to be selected from the sampling frame of 10 organizations to be compiled in the UK.

However, the research only managed to access seven organizations, as the other three turned down the interview on the grounds of privacy and confidentiality. The multi-case study facilitated an in-depth interview and analysis of the strategic management in NPOs to attain the research objectives.

A case study is suitable for confronting a particular organizational context. It is well adapted to explore complex organizational phenomena. This study of strategic management in NPOs relies on a qualitative case study.

The nonprofit sector is greatly heterogeneous and is characterized by a variety of organizations.

The focus of the study was to discover an area of investigation archetypal of the major features of NPOs and an analytic open to strategic management. Firstly, 10 NGOs were selected, which embody five attributes namely; -

- Organized and possess certain institutional realities
- Are private and tend to be institutionally distinct from government;
- Are non-profit-distributing and do not return any profit they make to donors or owners
- Are intrinsically voluntary and participating is not compulsory;
- Have reported steady growth in the last decade.

Being a phenomenological Study, data were collected using in-depth interviews to identify and interpret a participant's perceptions and constructed meanings. Document analysis was also used to compare the meanings to already documented ones (Creswell 1998). The significance of selecting a phenomenological study was to facilitate the pursuit of knowledge and personal construction of meanings.

3.4 Research Approach

The study used both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected using semi-structured interviews while secondary data was collected using document analysis.

The study relied on a mixed method of qualitative research approach. Data were collected using in-depth interviews and document analysis. The study used a qualitative research methodology owing to the qualitative nature of the research questions and objectives, which are oriented towards determining meanings associated with strategic management practices in non-profit organizations in the UK. According to Wilson & Chaddha (2010), a qualitative research approach is a research approach for identifying and resolving interplay of research participants' perspectives regarding a research phenomenon within a social or organizational setting.

Use of the mixed method approach provided evidence for a need to put together assorted data to answer the research questions. It mainly fitted for exploratory research because the research questions proposed may have formerly been addressed in previous pieces of research, yet not conclusively (Onwuegbuzie et al. 2012). For this reason, the approach was expected to improve the quality of the validity of previous research findings outside the UK, and in the process complement qualitative data. These provide a rationale for using document analysis and semi-structured interview survey in the study. Although document analysis provided data generated from documents that had attempted to examine strategic management in NPOs outside the UK, a semi-structured survey sought to validate such data within the context of NPOs that operate in the UK.

As a result, in the framework of this dissertation, the rationale for relying on mixed research method was built on the supposition that it would present a clarified point of view on strategic management in NPOs operating in the UK yet also respond to the research questions precisely.

Use of a mixed research method brought about five main benefits of the research.

- Triangulation: it allowed the researcher to use diverse types of methodologies and to ascertain the consistency of the results.
- Development: It enabled the researcher to employ the results generated from documents into those of a new study. For this reason, precedent knowledge was explored to construct new knowledge.
- Complementarity: It enabled corroboration of the validity of past research.

3.4.1 Semi-structured Interview

The study used in-depth semi-structured interviews. As qualitative research instruments, semi-structured interviews facilitate a study of individuals' perspectives, perceptions, opinions, viewpoints, meanings, and expectations. They facilitate an understanding of entrenched perceptions, and at the same time call upon comprehensible images or pictures of a research situation (Onwuegbuzie et al. 2012). The study used semi-structured interviews to complement document analysis. In doing this, it was expected that they would offer a deepened account of the attitudes, practices, and behaviors of leaders who use strategic management approaches in NPOs.

Use of semi-structured interviews allowed the participants to expand on issues they felt noteworthy for the study. It also allowed the researcher to ask questions outside the scope of review to facilitate in-depth research. It facilitated probing and asking follow-up questions. Also, it stimulated an emergence of unexpected concepts yet also facilitated the use of 'vignette questions.' Overall, the interviews range from being conversational to occasionally being rigid.

3.4.2 Document Analysis

This study also used document analysis, which entailed a systematic process of reviewing, appraisal, and interpreting research literature and related organizational documents to generate meanings and research knowledge. Document analysis was expected to balance data collected through in-depth interviews. According to Onwuegbuzie et al. (2012) document analysis can be used in combination with methods of research to add-on data collected and realize triangulation.

In this study, document analysis involved a systematic review, evaluation, and interpretation of varied documents to deduce meanings and develop a profound understanding of how NPOs in the UK approach and use strategic management models. Document analysis was appropriate for the study since it enabled access to information that was initially difficult to access in circumstances where participants were inaccessible. The method also eliminated research effect, where a researcher would have negatively affected the objectivity of the data analysis by integrating personal assumptions to influence the research results. However, the underlying motivation for using document analysis was because it was expected to enable scrutiny of changing trends of strategic management approaches in the NPOs in the UK. Accordingly, research reports, sectoral reports, and institutional reports enabled the researcher to track changes in strategic management practices over time.

3.5 Data Collection Method and Sampling Procedures

The researcher went for both primary and secondary data. Collection of primary data was through semi-structured interviews as the key research instrument. Conversely, a collection of secondary data was through document analysis. Seven semi-structured interviews were carried out. Semi-structured interviews were employed to collect participant's perspectives, which in turn complimented the information generated from a critical review of the literature on account of document analysis.

Participants were selected depending on their knowledge of strategic management in their organizations, in addition to their willingness to take part in the study. A majority of those interviewed requested that their identities and organizations remain anonymous. For this reason, the researcher treated their anonymity as an elemental ethical precondition. Although

the number of research participants was comparatively small, their perspectives covered a broad scope of stakeholder perceptions in addition to the totality of their perceptions on the subject of strategic management in NPOs in the U.K. The participants selected to take part in the study jointly exemplified the perspectives of the management and leadership of NPOs in the UK.

Before active collection of data, the researchers selected a sample of participants. The process of sampling entailed selection of a small sample of managers or leaders of NPOs in the UK to represent the population of study. This sampling criterion was significant owing to the researcher's limited resources; it lessened the effort of studying the entire population of managers and leaders of all NPOs in the UK. The selection of those who took part in the study was through a non-probability sampling method called convenience sampling. It was considered appropriate for the study because it facilitated the selection of participants based on how accessible they were and their willingness to take part in the study. Using this sampling method, the researcher managed to access 7 participants from 7 NPOs in the UK – although the researcher had targeted 15 participants from 10 NPOs.

The sampling approach had several drawbacks. Owing to its nature of being non-random, the researcher understood that there was a possibility that the sample selected would not necessarily represent the entire population of NPOs managers the study focused on. For this reason, the research approach is a comparatively weak sampling method. As a result, the research had minimal control over the sample's representativeness. Hence, the sample selected had a potential bias. Semi-structured interviews were undertaken in the 7 NPOs. The semi-structured interviews were undertaken with leaders of the organizations, mainly project manager, senior offers, coordinators, administrators, and CEOs. Basing on the interview questions on the literature, all interviews took an average of 50 minutes.

Analysis of data collected was performed using thematic analysis, which requires the use of four key steps for extraction of meaning. It was based on Miles and Huberman's (1994) framework for data analysis to facilitate extractions of meanings through data reduction, data display, drawing conclusion and verification of findings. These translate to different phases like familiarization with data, generation of initial codes, extracting themes, review of themes, definition, and naming of themes and generation of the report.

Data collected was initially passed through a process of data reduction to identify key categories that were viewed to potentially, address the research objectives. At this stage, redundant data was discarded. The next stage included the data display process (Guest et al., 2011). It helped organize and assemble data to ensure they are more compact and straightforward. Afterwards, conclusions were drawn to assist in the selection of relevant data patterns or themes in line with the research questions (Flick, 2014; Mason, 2002). The last stage involved data verification process (Thomas & Harden 2008; Bryman, 2008). Personal connections through the researcher's network of acquaintances were instrumental in recruiting the participants. The participants were first contacted by a covering mail to get their permission to conduct an interview. However, in two of the cases where the employees were interviewed, their HR department was contacted through a covering mail that explained the nature of the study.

In the process of data analysis, the identified data categories were then passed through a process of data display to organize and bring together data to make them more easily accessible, clear-cut, and compressed to facilitate easy generation of meaning. The next process involved the process of drawing conclusion, which entailed selection of relevant themes. Afterward, the process of data verification followed. This involved pragmatic review and assessment of the conclusions to determine their accuracy.

Overall, a convenience sampling approach was used to recruit all the participants. The participants who gave consent were separately issued participant information sheets that further described details of the study. Once the participants gave their consent, they were issued with participant information sheet that clarified to them the reasons for undertaking the

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study, what may be required from them in the process of the research, the benefits of taking part in the study, why they are an integral part of this research, the benefits and risks they may be exposed to by taking part in the study, and their primary rights as a participants.

However, to make sure that they also understood the content of the information sheet, the researcher explained to the research participants the study objectives, the methods to be used, the demands the research places on the participants, and the risks that they may face as research participants. The process was expected to make sure that participants were not coerced into taking part in the study. Rather, it was expected to make sure that the research participants adequately understand the right information or the implications of their involvement before willingly agreeing to take part in the study. The participants were also informed that they have a right to withdraw from the study at any point during the interview.

In an attempt to guarantee the confidentiality of collected data, the researcher maintained personal control and access to the data collected. Accordingly, data was stored on a password-protected computer. Participants' identities were kept anonymous; personal names were not included in the research results. Additionally, other identifying information were not disclosed. These include the names of their positions within the organization and the specific names of their organizations to ensure maximal anonymity. Some participants raised concerns regarding a need for total obscurity as the number of donors they can appeal to is contingent on the quality of reputation they command. Also, the answers provided were used exclusively for the study. No third party was allowed to access or physically handle the recording or the transcripts.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The researcher will collect and analyze data verbatim to make sure that the results reflect the true input of the research participants. The researcher will also seek consents from the targeted participants before interviewing them. The research will explain to the research participants the study objectives, scope, and demands on them before asking for their consent. The researcher will also ensure privacy and confidentiality of all individuals participating in the study, including by ensuring that they are kept anonymous.

4.0 Research Findings

This chapter presents analyses of data collected. The analysis is based on data-driven themes, which are based on the research questions that guided the study. Seven participants from seven NPOs were accessed. Their responses were analyzed concurrently before being compared against each other. This Chapter presents in-depth analysis and interpretation of data collected by relating them to the findings of several literature streams outlined in Chapter 2: Literature Review.

Several themes are described in-depth regarding the accompanying research findings. The results obtained, form the foundation for the final-conclusion in the final chapter. The in-depth analysis of research data was carried out basing on the participants' words before being interpreted into results by integrating them with relevant literature. To guarantee anonymity, the participants and organizations are not referred to using their names. Instead, they are tagged as P1 at NGO1 for the first participant and first organization or P2 and NGO2 for the second participant and second organization.

Participant 1 P(1) has 12 years of experience as a human resource manager at NGO1, which is a humanitarian NGOs. P2 is a program development manager with seven years of experience at NGO2, which is a development NGO. P3 is a CEO with 5 years of experience at NGO3, a child care organization, P4 is a project manager at NGO4, a religious and apostolic organization, P4 is a program coordinator at an NGO4, which is a foundation, P5 is a human resource manager at NGO 5, a social advocacy organization, P6 is a project manager at NGO6, a public charity. P7 is a program coordinator at NGO7, a humanitarian organization.

What Strategic Management Practices do your Organization Use?

P1, P2, P5, and P7 were of the opinion that their strategic management practices are largely influenced by external factors like donors and clients, who have dominant control over who should control the capital, legitimacy, and labor. As they have scarce resources, donors have greater leverage over the practices they should adopt to appeal to them.

P1 said:

“Our organization’s strategic management practice mainly entails sitting down whenever there is a foreseeable problem in our future external problem to put up goals and a vision that is capable of provides a sense of purpose and direction for each one in the organization and those we related with, like our donors.”

P2 said:

Consistent with these assumptions, Rehor et al. (2014) argued that a significant number of dynamics of shifts to the external environment and the complexity of the entire strategic management process. They also showed that the failure or success of NPOs is essentially contingent on strategic decision-making. This indicates that strategic management practices are largely influenced by external stakeholders and designed for problem-solving. According to Rehor et al. (2014), they are a combination of management decisions and action plans that the management can employ to enable competitive advantage and long-term better performance of an organization. As a consequence, it potentially reduces organizational weaknesses and leverages their strengths by anticipating prospects and problems.

P3 had their strategic management practices oriented towards the internal environment.

P3 said:

“We do a lot in terms of strategic management... As the CEO, I have done much to develop an organizational culture that enables each member of the organization to identify and develop a sense of belonging and shared values to attain future goals.... By members of the organization, I mean the board, management, and general staff. Our strategic management has been instrumental in enhancing each member’s level of motivation to attain common goals.

It is only P4 and P6, whose strategic management practices are aimed at both the internal and external environment.

P4 said: “I have been greatly involved in setting up strategic management practice, which in my opinion are tactical managerial decisions and skills that directly affect our organization’s capacity to respond to the needs of our beneficiaries and wishes of our funders and the needs of our employees. We set up strategic plans and goals with a focus on those areas, and to ultimately move in a new direction whenever there is a problem.

P4 and P6 attempted to show that what is significant for strategic management practices is making sure that focus is placed on both external and internal strategic objectives.

Related literature has indicated that strategic management should make sure that organizational management does not occur randomly but that they are based on clarified long-term objectives (Weerawardena & Mort, 2012). Weerawardena and Mort (2012) also clarified that NPO leaders should be open to shifting goals and activities with regards to changing situations in the external or internal environments. As a result, organizational leaders need to consistently, monitor, evaluate, and benefit from constant feedback. It is on this basis that strategic management could be reasoned as a fluid, and ongoing approach, as opposed to a one-shot approach. Rehor et al. (2014) also argued that strategic management should also be considered as a process and a means of contemplating about particular aspects of an organization like long- and short-term goals, stakeholders, and achieving efficiency. It is a continuous intricate process of management that agrees on the organizational targets and a strategic course for reaching specific targets.

To this end, it can only be concluded that a majority of the NPOs in the UK have defective strategic management practices targeted at external environment, other than both the internal and external environment.

P2 said that their organization is overwhelmed by the growing number of NGOs that compete for funds, which forces them to focus their strategies on winning the increasingly scarce donors. We must ensure that the organization is sustainable in the long term. Consistent with this, Mort and Weerawardena (2008) established that more NGOs are focusing on ensuring the sustainability. However, they appear to disagree with P2 when they assert that nonprofit literature seems not to reveal that NPOs have emphasized on attaining competitive advantages to enable them to grow and survive over the long-term, in spite of an increasing rate of threats to their sustainability. Weerawardena et al. (2010) had also observed that NPOs must lay a comparatively lower emphasis on clients than on donors.

What Strategic Model does your Organization Use?

All participants showed that their organizations are niche strategists, which Ogonji (2014) defines as “organizations that stick to their missions and objectives and have not considered had expanded beyond their niche.” Only NGO4 has attempted to use a market-orientation model to get money flowing into NGO4, which is an educational foundation.

P4 said:

“... We are an educational foundation. Providing bursaries to students in and outside the UK is becoming very much costly. On the other hand, we have had few donations coming in the last couple of years. However, we learned that the more students we sponsor, the more attractive our organization looks. So, we want as much as possible to treat our clients well. When they speak well of us, more money keep on coming.

Hence, the focus of NGO4 is appealing and satisfying customers. Consistent with this, Weerawardena et al. (2010) demonstrated that few NPOs use the “market orientation” model and the “market-driven firm paradigm,” which are substantially employed in for-profit organizations to satisfy and retain customers. However, there seems to be discontent with NGO4’s approach in current literature. Weerawardena et al. (2010) argued that while focusing on clients has a potential to ensure better service delivery in NPOs, the link between the clients and generation of revenue is fundamentally detached in NPOs.

P1, P2, P3, P6, and P7 use the donor-oriented model to appeal to more funding from donors.

P2 said: “I don’t believe what we do is unique. As there is an implied understanding that the type of sector we operate in has an unwritten rule that we are not allowed to engage in active marketing, the manner in which we can advertise ourselves to donors is limited, unless of course there is a humanitarian crisis. So, we want to be as transparent as possible, to be as accountable as possible and to rely on word-of-mouth advertising to tell our able donors that their funds are helping a social cause.”

From the review of the literature, there is a considerable understanding that NPOs use donor-oriented models of strategic management (Weerawardena et al. 2010). They place donors at the center of their appeal, owing to the decisive role they play in the provision of revenue stream that is significant for the operation of an NPO.

The approach pursued by a majority of NPOs in the UK, whereby they emphasize donor-oriented models are inconsistent with Weerawardena’s et al. (2010) idea that NPOs could focus on ‘balancing money and mission’ as the principal concern in the management of NPOs. Weerawardena’s et al. (2010) considered organizations that use this model as characterized by using constructs like production quality, pricing, production quantity, improvement of service quality, and budgeting practice.

Evidently, a majority of NPOs in the UK have not considered using the ‘earned income strategies’ and “market-oriented model.” In the last decade, some scholars have arrived at a consensus that ‘earned income strategies’ can be used to attain organizational sustainability, which integrates the attributes of nonprofit with for-profit organizations (Peredo & McLean, 2006; Weerawardena et al. (2010). The profits that these organizations generate from their principal activities are applied in engaging in numerous social ventures (Seelos & Mair, 2005).

In what ways do your Strategic Management Practices of NPOs differ from those of for-profit organizations?

The 7 participants said that their organization's strategic management practices differ from those of for-profit organizations, as they mostly aim to attain greater production quantity, reduced expenses, and quality service with the view to appeal to more donations. According to Weerawardena et al. (2010), for-profit organizations are focused on improvement in production quality, pricing, cost-cutting measures and improvement of service quality with the view of making more profits.

P5 said: "Obviously, we operate differently as we are not interested in making profits. Not that we would not appreciate profits, but the structure of our organization directs that we help rather than profit. Mostly, we emphasize production quantity to help more people and appeal to more donors. We also must operate within our budget, including by cutting expenses whenever necessary. This is risky, as it limits our potential for efficiency.

Consistent with this perspective, studies have based their assumptions on the principal–agency theory to argue that for-profit organizations tend to be more efficient than nonprofit organizations as for-profit organizations aspire to make profits and increase shareholders' returns (Reeves & Ford 2004). The tendency to constantly cut operating expenses makes nonprofit organizations to constantly have lower levels of daily adjusted costs compared to for-profit organizations. Indeed, related literature has also demonstrated that a market-oriented mindset has significant advantages over donor-oriented mindsets in terms of encouraging efficiency in profit-driven business firms. It encourages organizations to design the most suitable services to the target clients and can enable sustainable competitive advantage by encouraging organizations to create superior customer value and better organizational performance (Macedo & Pinho 2004; Othman et al. 2014).

How does NPO's external environmental and internal context and strategy formation processes influence the strategies they use?

All the 7 participants agreed that external environmental and internal environment influences the strategy formation processes and the strategies use. This is in spite of the idea that 4 of the participants have strategic management practices principally designed for the external environment.

P2 said: "Yeah! Both the external and internal environment threatens our existence. But, I have worked here long enough as a human resource manager to understand that the organization is more terrified by the idea of increasingly diminishing donations and funding from the government than the relatively high employee turnover."

P5 said that their organization had realized a need to develop new missions annually in an attempt to appeal to a new base of donors who may favor a newer mission.

These ideas were explored in previous research. According to Othman et al. (2014), because of slow funding, non-profit managers increasingly realize that their new missions are to constantly, influence donors to donate, volunteers to volunteer, clients to come for help, and employees to be client-friendly, accountable and transparent. Some scholars have argued that adopting resource-based strategies can enable NPOs to adopt a change of attitude with respect to obtaining and managing their funding sources and their management strategies. Put differently, NPOs must seek ways to efficiently manage their resources more efficiently to improve their performance in an increasingly complex internal and external environment (Macedo & Pinho 2004; Othman et al. 2014).

While P3 agreed that their organization has to monitor the internal and external environment constantly, they have to constantly protect their key resources, including the board, which is made up of the funders, the managers, and the need to constantly plan for the future. An earlier study demonstrated that some of the internal indicators that enhance the urgency for planning, particularly in the increasingly aggressive nonprofit environment. These include periods of stagnant

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organizational growth and administrative operations, and high employee turnover or changes in leadership (Giffords and Dina 2004). P3's assumption is built on the resource dependence theory, which contends that organizations can attain ultimate survival depending on their capacity to obtain and maintain resources (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978, p. 2).

However, the tendency to focus on the internal environment by NPOs in the UK is not advocated in current literature. According to Giffords and Dina (2004), a tendency to concentrate on the internal environment would enable the managers may discover conflicting perspectives of the organization's mission and vision, and degree of efficiency. However, they may as well find themselves becoming increasingly immersed in the everyday operation of the organizations, which may influence them to concentrate on "program ends rather than the purpose" they are intended to accomplish, including attending to the needs of the clients. Hence, while organizational cultures and values should as well be taken into consideration as they directly affect the organization's operation, external factors like client needs and donor demands should also be considered (Romney, 2001). This is because the external environment is also crucial for the well-functioning of NPOs, particularly in periods where there is a high competition for limited funds, changes in client priorities, Shifts in accreditation requirements, and societal changes (Romney, 2001).

P4 and P6 stated that their organizations have always aimed to achieve a balance between addressing their external and internal environmental problems, as part of their long-term strategy. According to Giffords and Dina (2004), the main advantage of creating a strategic plan within the framework of continuous quality and performance improvement (CQPI) is to enable nonprofit's management and employees to acclimatize the organization to the existing internal and external environment, prioritize the organization's mission, and illuminate client's needs. This will enable NPOs to continually improve quality services to their clients while revealing to their funders and other concerned stakeholders that the organization has a positive effect on them.

How does your organization set up strategic management strategies in response to changes in the internal and external environment?

All the 7 participants mentioned that they rely on strategic planning to set up strategic management strategies.

P4 said: "Strategic planning. We have traditionally used strategic planning. It is a complex problem-solving process for the future. I guess that's how it should be described." P7 said that they first evaluate an organization's performance and identify areas where there is a need to execute targeted improvements rapidly.

There appears to be an agreement in current research regarding the use of strategic planning to set up strategic management strategies. Although researchers agree on the use of strategic planning, there are a variety of strategic planning processes. Although the participants did not mention any of strategic planning processes by name, they appeared to focus on the continuous process of evaluating their organization's performance against external and internal environmental factors.

This form of the strategic planning process is what Giffords and Dina (2004) call continuous quality and performance improvement (CQPI). As Giffords and Dina (2004) elaborated, most NPOs use CQPI to adjust to the changing external and internal environments. Pecora and Seelig (2001), who consider a CQPI plan as a systematic process that enables NPOs to set up plans to improve in all areas of their operation, support the idea. Giffords and Dina (2004) view it as an organization's pledge to its clients and the greater community to offer them efficient and effective services. According to Mikulas and Cohan (2001), setting up a CQPI means that that the planning, goal-setting and attainment activities of an organization are provided with information using a formal feedback process, including through external assessments, to bring about improved performance that is beneficial to both the organization and its constituents.

What reasons underlie the use of strategic management in your organization?

The participants suggested varied reasons that motivate their organizations to engage in strategic management. P1, P2, P5, and P7 mentioned that they continually engage in strategic planning to overcome the growing competition for

donations. All participants mentioned that they resort to strategic planning when they face problems in the acquisition of finances. P3 and P4 mentioned that they considered engaging strategic management when looking for partnerships with other organizations. P4 and P6 stated that they considered it appropriate to engage in strategic management to respond to a growing need for transparency and accountability by their donors. In all, all the participants agree that strategic planning enabled them to make informed decisions regarding their futures.

These views are adequately supported in the previous literature. According to Ogonji (2014), strategic management enables organizations to adjust to environmental factors that may threaten their futures and to agree on what should be done to get there by adopting new approaches. Bryson (2010) established that strategic management encourages strategic thinking and actions to respond to a situational issue in an organization. It leads to a clarification of vision, assists organizations to discover best strategies, promotes consensus- building among stakeholders and improves the capacity of organizations to make a quality decision that reflects back to organizational objectives and mission.

The researcher also outlined that strategic management also becomes useful when organizations change their scope of operation or mission. At any rate, Bryson (2010) and Ogonji (2014) agreed that it is the challenges that NPOs have to constantly address in the internal and external environments that motivate them to set up strategic management measures. The researchers outlined that substantial rise in demand for services that NPOs offer, a greater level of competition, problems in the acquisition of funds, a desire to collaborate with other organizations, greater pressures for transparency and accountability and increased levels of doubt regarding economic, political and social changes of the future prompted NPOs to engage in strategic management.

5.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the results of the findings established through the in-depth analysis before being interpreted through perspectives of several literature streams outlined in Chapter 4 are presented. The results are described in detail proportionate to their associated research findings.

Result 1: Strategic management practices used by NPOs in the UK

A majority of the participants elaborated that strategic management practices are largely influenced by external factors like donors and clients, who have dominant control over who should control the capital, legitimacy, and labor. Apparently, because NPOs have scarce financial resources and depend significantly on their donors, the donors have greater leverage over the practices they should adopt to appeal to them. This reasoning has a theoretical basis, as it is well explained by the resource dependence theory, which hypothesizes that an organization's behavior depends on the degree of its resource dependencies (Hillman et al. 2009). In other words, external factors like donors are always bound to influence the strategies and decisions of NPOs.

Accordingly, NPOs make strategic management practices to survive, yet since they require resources like capital, labor, legitimacy, and clientele, their strategic depend on the external factors control, which causes interdependencies that may contribute to an imbalance of power over who should control the NPOs. Since the finances they require in their operations are scarce, the funders or donors have greater power. This potentially leads the organization to lose autonomy and an ability to freely undertake managerial and strategic discretion as required (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978).

Accordingly, the that strategic management practices adopted by NPOs in the UK are largely influenced by external stakeholders and intended to solve problems they expect to meet in their external environments, such as a greater level of competition for donations and, problems in the acquisition of funds (Rehor et al. 2014). Therefore, for NPOs in the UK, strategic management practices amount to a combination of management decisions and action plans that these

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organizations employ to achieve competitive advantage and attain long-term better performance. Additionally, strategic management practices potentially reduce organizational weaknesses and leverage their strengths by anticipating prospects and problems.

To this end, it can only be concluded that a majority of the NPOs in the UK have defective strategic management practices targeted at external environment, other than both the internal and external environment. There appears to be a consensus among researchers that the strategic management practices oriented towards both the internal environment. This can ensure that NPOs effectively adjust to changing situations in the external or internal environments (Rehor et al. 2014). This will also ensure that NPOs are reaching their specific targets while managing all stakeholder expectations, whether their donors or clients, in a balanced manner.

Result 2: Strategic management models used by NPOs

A majority of participants agreed that their organizations are niche strategists. This implies that they adhere to the specific missions and objectives and do not consider expanding beyond their areas of operation to expand their sources of funds. A majority of the NPOs also appear to use the donor-orientation model, as their focus is on countering growing competition for donations to appeal to more donors. Again, this finding has a theoretical basis in the resource dependence theory, which views these NPOs as focused on attaining ultimate survival depending on their capacity to acquire and maintain resources (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978, p. 2). Accordingly, NPOs will tend to adopt the donor-orientation model, as it enables them to attain and maintain their funding resources. For this reason, it is understandable that NPOs in the UK will place donors at the center of their operations because of the crucial role they play in sustaining their revenue stream.

However, there is also a concern that NPOs should pursue a more balanced model that emphasizes on both donors and clients or a model that Weerawardena's et al. (2010) suggests that can help the NPOs to 'balance money and mission.' Fundamentally, this model is discussed in the literature as more effective owing to its potential to assist organizations to focus on a wide variety of operational variables like production quality, service quality, production quantity, donor management, and effective budgeting practices.

Result 3: How strategic practices of NPOs differ from those of for-profit organizations

A majority of the participants said that their organization's strategic management practices differ from those of for-profit organizations, as they mostly aim to attain greater production quantity, reduced expenses, and quality service with the view to appeal to more donations. Again, this idea can be explained by the resource dependence theory, which hypothesizes that an organization's management practices and decision-making depend on the degree of its resource dependencies (Hillman et al. 2009). In other words, external factors like donors are always bound to influence the strategies and decisions of NPOs. Using this perspective, it could be reasoned as for-profit organizations are more driven by a need to make more profits and increase their shareholder's wealth, as they depend on shareholders for capital resources. Hence, NPOs and for-profit organizations are bound to have differing strategic management practices. However, this variation also explains the different levels of efficiency between NPOs and for-profit organizations. On account of the principal–agency theory, it can be reasoned that for-profit organizations tend to be more efficient than nonprofit organizations as for-profit organizations are driven to make profits and increase shareholders' returns (Reeves & Ford 2004). This also demonstrates that a market-oriented mindset has significant advantages over donor-oriented mindsets in terms of encouraging efficiency in profit-driven business firms. It encourages organizations to design the most suitable services to the target clients and can enable sustainable competitive advantage by encouraging organizations to create superior customer value and better organizational performance (Othman et al. 2014).

Result 4: Effects of NPO's external environmental and internal context on strategy formation processes

All participants agreed that the external environmental and internal environment influences the strategy formation processes and the strategies that their organizations use. Consistent with the resource-dependency theory and NPOs' dependence on donors, these organizations continually realize a need to develop new missions while seeking to appeal to a new base of donors. Indeed, because of slow funding, NPOs whose missions cannot capture the appeal of donors have to change their missions (Othman et al. 2014).

However, there I also an agreement among participants and researchers that adopting resource-based strategies would allow NPOs to find and manage all forms of resources, including funding and labor resources, in a fairly balanced manner. This appears to be the case in the UK, whereby NPOs must seek ways to efficiently manage their resources more efficiently to improve their performance in an increasingly complex internal and external environment. These organizations should aim to achieve a balance between addressing their external and internal environmental problems, as part of their long-term strategy.

Result 5: Organizational response to changes in the internal and external environment

All the 7 participants mentioned that they rely on strategic planning to set up strategic management strategies to respond to shifts in the internal and external environment. While there appears to be an agreement on the use of strategic planning by the response, the types and focus vary, as a majority of the strategies targeted at the external environment. However, it is clear that their strategies are intended to ensure the continuous process of improving and evaluating organizational performance. In strategic planning literature, there appears to be a contention that NPOs should consider integrating CQPI to continually adapt to the shifts in their external and internal environments. Indeed, it is well supported in current literature that organizations should focus their strategic planning on their external and internal environments, rather than exclusively the internal or external environment (Pecora & Seelig 2001; Giffords & Dina 2004). Accordingly, use of CQPI by UK NPOs would imply that these organizations engage in planning, goal-setting, and periodic assessments to bring enabled improved performance to the benefit of the organization and its stakeholders.

Result 6: Reasons for strategic management by NPOs

A majority of participants contend that their organizations are mostly motivated to engage strategic management in competing for donations. However, there is also an agreement among researchers that they take on strategic management to collaborate with stakeholders and other organizations and to ensure transparency and accountability by their donors. Current literature supports these findings. These translate to a drive-by NPOs to take on strategic management to respond to their external and internal environments

These views are adequately supported in the previous literature. Indeed, there appears to be an agreement among researchers that NPOs often adopt strategic management practices to manage their internal and external resources adequately. However, it appears that taking on strategic management to attract donors forms the principal rationale for NPOs to engage in strategic management. Guided by the resource-dependence theory, NPOs will accommodate strategic practices depending on the degree of the resource dependencies on certain stakeholders. In other words, their strategies are mostly focused on attracting donors, as they depend significantly on them for financial resources. In all, strategic management enables these organizations to respond to situational issues in an organization, whereby addressing their financial resources is merely one of those issues (Bryson 2010).

6.0 Conclusion

The research aimed to explore the strategic management practices in NPOs operating in the UK. NPOs in the UK find it difficult gaining absolute control over the affairs and the environment in which their organizations operate in the twenty-first century. In addition, they have either failed or have been slow to adopt strategic management “best practices.”

It is established in this research that external stakeholders and environmental influence strategic management practices that NPOs in the UK employ. The practices are mainly designed to solve problems expected in the external environments. On top of these problems include a greater level of competition for donations and problems in the acquisition of funds. This illustrates that NPOs in the UK have defective strategic management practices targeted at external environment, other than both the internal and external environment. It is recommended that NPOs in the UK must seek ways to efficiently manage their resources more efficiently to improve their performance in an increasingly complex internal and external environment. These organizations should aim to achieve a balance between addressing their external and internal environmental problems, as part of their long-term strategy. NPOs in the UK should pursue a more balanced model that emphasizes on both donors and clients, or a model potentially enables them to ‘balance money and mission.’

The research has added knowledge on the significance of having strategic management practices designed to achieve a balance between addressing NPOs external and internal environmental problems. This model is found to be more effective as it enables these organizations to focus on a wide variety of operational variables like production quality, service quality, production quantity, donor management, and effective budgeting practices. This can be explained by the resource dependence theory. NPOs’ strategic management practices differ from those of for-profit organizations, as they mostly aim to attain greater production quantity, reduced expenses, and quality service with the view to appeal to more donations. On account of the principal–agency theory, it is established that for-profit organizations tend to be more efficient than nonprofit organizations as for-profit organizations are driven to make profits and increase shareholders’ returns. This also demonstrates that a market-oriented mindset has significant advantages over donor-oriented mindsets in terms of encouraging efficiency in profit-driven business firms. It encourages organizations to design the most suitable services to the target clients and can enable sustainable competitive advantage by encouraging organizations to create superior customer value and better organizational performance.

This research has some limitations. As the study sample was fairly small, the study results have a narrow capacity for generalizability. Also, the participants were interviewed within a small timeframe depending on their accessibility. This was detrimental as it restricted the number of respondents who the researcher could access. Although a few participants were approached, they are assumed to be a representative of a broad cross-section of perspectives of the managers and leaders of NPOs. Another limitation is related to the sampling method. The convenience sampling used had some drawbacks. Because of its non-random in nature, the sample selected may be assumed as not representing the entire target population of UK NPOs that the study focused on.

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